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Review Article

**REVIEW OF CHRONIC RENAL DISEASE MANAGEMENT IN
FAMILY MEDICINE**

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¹Northern Border University²Taibah University³University of Sciences and Technology -Sana'a⁴Wroclaw Medical University⁵Umm Alqura University⁶King Khalid University⁷Arabian Gulf University⁸Taibah University⁹King Abdulaziz University¹⁰King Saud University**Abstract:**

Because chronic kidney disease is a growing health concern, primary physicians must be equipped to care for this unique patient population. In this review we discuss the criteria, diagnosis and management methods of CKD. Electronic searches of the PubMed, EMBASE, and Cochrane Library databases were conducted for the purposes of conducting a narrative review of all studies concerning Chronic renal disease management in family medicine published in English language up to August, 2018. Family physicians play a key function in ensuring that individuals with chronic kidney illness obtain proper counseling and health maintenance treatments; this is a pivotal part to effective management of chronic kidney disease. Immunizations that are suggested for all chronic kidney disease patients are influenza and pneumovax vaccinations. Once a patient develops stage 4 chronic kidney illness, they ought to likewise receive the hepatitis B series because hemodialysis patients are at a raised risk of exposure to hepatitis B, in spite of cautions. Diabetes mellitus and hypertension, which are frequently managed in the workplace setting, are the largest contributors to chronic kidney condition; for that reason, these danger aspects ought to be tightly controlled and these patients must be screened closely for indications of kidney damages. Further health maintenance measures should be executed according to the patient's other disease-specific suggestions and age.

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INTRODUCTION:

Chronic kidney disease (CKD) or chronic renal disease (CRD) is common with an estimated worldwide prevalence of 11-13% [1]. CKD prevalence is rising, driven by an aging populace and also the increasing prevalence of obesity, diabetes and hypertension [1]. Because of this, CKD provides an increasing worry to health services. The majorities of patients with mild to moderate CKD are asymptomatic, but have a greater risk of cardiovascular disease and go to danger of developing anemia, metabolic bone illness or progressing to end-stage renal disease (ESRD) requiring renal replacement therapy (RRT) [1]. Interventions recommended to lower the danger of these endpoints include diet and lifestyle modification, anti-hypertensive drug (specifically inhibitors of the renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system), lipid modification, as well as attaining glycemic control in patients with diabetes mellitus [2].

Patients with minor to moderate CKD are usually maintained within primary care and sent to professional care as the problem advances. Nonetheless, initiatives to boost the awareness of CKD have actually led to the identification of great deals of patients with mild to moderate CKD, producing difficulties in the design and delivery of health services [2]. How health services must be organized to support patients with CKD most effectively, is unclear [2].

The existing literature on treatments to enhance outcomes in CKD is of primarily individual interventions, e.g. psychological support, pharmacist medication review, anti-hypertensive medicine [2]. In professional technique, many individual treatments are used together for a specific patient. This multidimensional technique, arranging packages of treatments forms a 'model of care'. Comprehending the ideal version of care for CKD patients is important and also would allow the design of health services to optimize health and well-being whilst making finest use of limited sources.

Because chronic kidney disease is a growing health concern, primary physicians must be equipped to care

for this unique patient population. In this review we discuss the criteria, diagnosis and management methods of CKD.

METHODOLOGY:

Electronic searches of the PubMed, EMBASE, and Cochrane Library databases were conducted for the purposes of conducting a narrative review of all studies concerning Chronic renal disease management in family medicine published in English language up to August, 2018. manual searching of reference lists was also performed.

DISCUSSION:**• Definition**

The National Kidney Foundation specifies CKD as any problems of kidney functionality as confirmed by lowered glomerular filtration rate (GFR) or other proof of kidney damage, the latter including proteinuria, hematuria, uncommon kidney biopsy, or irregular renal imaging report [4] (Table 1). CKD can be categorized into 1 of 5 stages with CKD stage 5 including patients with GFR < 15 mL/min along with patients with end-stage renal disease (ESRD) on dialysis (Table 2). Although patients with CKD may not need dialysis up until they get to stage 5, the complications from CKD itself (anemia, metabolic bone condition, acidosis, and also poor nutrition) as well as associated comorbid problems (cardiovascular disease, diabetes mellitus, as well as high blood pressure) can be seen at a lot earlier stages as well as aggravate as the condition advances. In fact, patients with phase 3 as well as phase 4 CKD are far more most likely to die, normally from cardiovascular disease, than to advance to ESRD [2]. Late medical diagnosis of CKD, late or absence of referral to the nephrologist, and failure to apply established care guidelines all result in poor results in CKD patients [3]. Likewise, failure to identify and treat complications of ESRD, deal with comorbid conditions, and offer preventative care such as immunizations leads to inadequate outcomes, consisting of avoidable hospital stays. Such suboptimal care for CKD and ESRD individuals is the intended of disease-management (DM) programs for these vulnerable individuals.

Table 1. Definition of Chronic Kidney Disease Criteria [3].

1. Kidney damage for ≥ 3 months, as defined by structural or functional abnormalities of the kidney, with or without decreased GFR, manifest by either: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pathological abnormalities; or • Markers of kidney damage, including abnormalities in the composition of the blood or urine, or abnormalities in imaging tests
2. GFR < 60 mL/min/1.73 m ² for ≥ 3 months, with or without kidney damage

Abbreviation: GFR, glomerular filtration rate.

Table 2. Stages of Chronic Kidney Disease (Age >20) [1].

Stage	Description	GFR (mL/min/1.73 m ²)
1	Kidney damage with normal or [GFR	≥ 90
2	Kidney damage with mild Y GFR	60–89
3	Moderate Y GFR	30–59
4	Severe Y GFR	15–29
5	Kidney failure	< 15 (or dialysis)

Abbreviation: GFR, glomerular filtration rate.

- **Identifying people with CKD**

Understanding the description and staging of CKD is crucial to appropriately identify individuals with the condition in clinical practice. Such details are likewise a crucial to suitably recommend patients about their kidney wellness and stratify their future danger.

Diagnostic criteria

Basing on to the KDIGO CKD guidelines (and the English National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE) CKD standards), a patient is determined with CKD if abnormalities of kidney structure or function were present for a minimum of 3 months [5]. The abnormalities are shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Diagnostic criteria for CKD [5].

<p>One of the following needs to be present for at least 3 months:</p> <p>a) Decreased eGFR (< 60 mL/min/1.73 m²)</p> <p>b) One or more marker of kidney damage:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> i. Albuminuria (urinary albumin-to-creatinine ratio [ACR] ≥ 30 mg/g [3 mg/mmol]) ii. Structural abnormalities (from imaging) iii. Urine sediment abnormalities (hematuria, red or white blood cell casts, oval fat bodies or fatty casts, granular casts, and renal tubular epithelial cells) iv. Electrolyte and other abnormalities due to tubular disorders v. Histological abnormalities vi. Previous history of kidney transplantation
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Abbreviations: CKD, chronic kidney disease; eGFR, estimated glomerular filtration rate.

In practice, in primary care, the most essential procedures to identify CKD are eGFR stemmed from serum creatinine and also ACR derived from a urine example. NICE recommends that specific populaces must be used testing for CKD using eGFR and ACR Table 4.

Table 4. People with any of the following risk factors should be offered testing for CKD [5].

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diabetes • Hypertension • Acute kidney injury • Cardiovascular disease (ischemic heart disease, chronic heart failure, peripheral vascular disease, or cerebral vascular disease) • Structural renal tract disease, renal calculi, or prostatic hypertrophy • Multisystem diseases with potential kidney involvement, for example, systemic lupus erythematosus • Family history of end-stage kidney disease (GFR category G5) or hereditary kidney disease • Opportunistic detection of hematuria

Estimated glomerular filtration rate

Standardized equations to derive eGFR from serum creatinine are required due to the fact that creatinine is an incomplete sign of renal excretory function, influenced by various other aspects (consisting of muscle mass, age, sex, ethnicity, comorbidities, injury, workout, and also high protein diet) [6]. The usual equations in use by laboratories are the modified diet in kidney illness and the Chronic Kidney Disease Epidemiology Collaboration (CKDEPI) [6]. The CKDEPI is a more accurate equation, as well as its use in a populace has a tendency to decrease the prevalence of CKD however identify a greater threat population [6]. This has been shown in a large size, population-based research study in the UK in which an adjustment to the CKDEPI formula was connected with a decrease in general CKD stage G3-G5 prevalence, but a boost in individuals older than 70 years and also in the Health Survey for England (which is population representative) in which CKD G3-G5 prevalence was minimized from 6% to 5.2% by the usage of CKDEPI [7].

Cystatin C is an additional measure of renal function where eGFR can be discovered, less affected by muscular tissue mass, although it is more expensive and also not yet in common use in lots of locations [8].

Proteinuria

There has actually been considerable discussion concerning various methods of proteinuria identification, including the function of urine dipsticks and protein-to-creatinine proportion. This has actually triggered some confusion amongst primary care practitioners. While dipstick examinations can discover albumin, they may be much less efficient finding other urinary healthy proteins and are poor at protein metrology, and ACR has been shown to have higher sensitivity than protein-to-creatinine ratio for lower levels of proteinuria [9]. There is evidence suggesting that a solitary ACR, specifically if measured on an early morning urine sample, is a sufficiently sensitive examination to determine albuminuria [9]. These issues were ruled out in further information here, as international guidelines are moving toward a consensus viewpoint, and KDIGO now plainly suggests ACR as the investigation of option and a solitary early morning urine example adequate to identify proteinuria [10].

In clinical practice, although these distinguishing standards are clear, it can be challenging to apply them. As an example, blood and urine tests may

require to be repeated in order to recognize the chronicity of kidney dysfunction, and also the time of replay testing requires to be carefully taken into consideration. When an eGFR <60 mL/min/1.73 m² is determined in an individual with previously normal renal function, the first step is to verify the result and to exclude the opportunity that the individual is establishing transient elevation of creatinine (and fall in eGFR) associated with other factors, such as AKI, by repeat testing within a brief time period. The NICE guidelines recommend "Confirm an eGFR outcome of <60 mL/min/1.73 m² in an individual not previously examined by repeating the examination within 2 weeks" [5].

- **Interventions to Slow the Progression of Kidney Disease**

The Modification of Diet in Renal Disease study [12] followed chronic renal disease individuals at all stages for a 2-year period and completed that 85% of individuals had a decrease in their GFR, with the average rate of decline 4 mL/min every year despite the baseline GFR. There are flexible and nonmodifiable variables that contribute to this decline. These variables have been shown to be considerable despite the rooting etiology of the chronic kidney disease. In general, the nonmodifiable danger factors related to more rapid decrease in kidney illness consist of increased age, African-American race, and male gender. The modifiable danger variables are the focus of treatment to suspend disease development and include higher levels of proteinuria, a lower serum albumin level, increased blood pressure, bad glycemic control, and smoking cigarettes. Presently there is opposing information regarding the role of dyslipidemia and anemia in the function of kidney disease progression [11].

Proteinuria

Because proteinuria adds to a boost in kidney damage, testing and metrology of the existence of proteinuria is vital in the care of chronic kidney disease patients. Random (spot) examples of urine for calculation of the urine protein-creatinine proportion eliminate the requirement for 24-hour urine collections for quantification of proteinuria. Once proteinuria is determined, its control comes to be a high concern. The goal of treatment is to reduce the level of proteinuria; even reduced levels of proteinuria are related to progression of chronic kidney illness and cardiovascular disease [11].

Angiotensin transforming enzyme (ACE) inhibitors are considered first-line medicines for proteinuria, regardless of the underlying cause or stage of chronic kidney condition [11]. Therefore, family doctor

should become proficient with the admission of these medications and confidence with monitoring their effects. Because hyperkalemia and minor deterioration of renal function can occur with the initiation of ACE inhibitors, these factors need to be monitored; however, the drugs ought to not be discontinued without due cause. Mild hyperkalemia (potassium < 5.6 mmol/L) can usually be managed by dietary modifications, cessation of NSAID use, and potassium-sparing diuretics, if relevant. Additionally, potassium excretion can be enhanced by the addition of a loop diuretic. For hyperkalemia >5.6 mmol/L, the ACE inhibitor need to be instantly terminated and the patient needs to be managed properly. With regard to the issue of acute kidney failure pertaining to the initiation of ACE inhibitors, a moderate increase in creatinine level (<30% rise) within 1 to 2 weeks of beginning of therapy is considered appropriate. The patient ought to be monitored to ensure that additional rise does not take place since this would be trigger for discontinuation of medicine and further assessment. Renal artery stenosis, hypovolemia, or uncompensated heart failure might be associated with an increase in creatinine level of >30% and, when managed, the ACE inhibitor might be renewed securely [13].

An angiotensin receptor blocker (ARB) may be thought about for individuals who are unable to endure ACE inhibitors. In diabetic kidney condition, an ARB may be used as a first-line alternative to ACE inhibitors [18] Furthermore, the candesartan and lisinopril microalbuminuria research study demonstrated the benefit of the usage of the mix of an ACE inhibitor (lisinopril) with an ARB (candesartan) in individuals with diabetic-associated microalbuminuria [14] The inclusion of a nondihydropyridine calcium channel blocker, such as diltiazem or verapamil, can further decrease the degree of proteinuria, as can the addition of a thiazide or loop diuretic [11] Nevertheless, the blockade of the renin-angiotensin system remains the cornerstone of treatment of proteinuria.

Blood Pressure Control

Precise blood pressure control is a significant concern in the care of the individual with chronic kidney disease. For the reasons discussed over, ACE inhibitors or ARBs are frequently used as the

preliminary medicines to accomplish blood pressure control; nevertheless, typically a multidrug regimen is needed. Frequently, diuretics are required for patients with chronic kidney condition because of the hypertensive impact of quantity overload [15]. According to the Seventh Report of the Joint National Committee on Prevention, Detection, Evaluation, and Treatment of High Blood Pressure standards, [16] the aim blood pressure is >130/80 mm Hg in individuals with chronic kidney illness; nevertheless, the National Kidney Foundation [11] recommends an extra stringent objective of >125/75 mm Hg for patients with chronic kidney condition and significant proteinuria. With the accomplishment of these blood pressure goals, additionally kidney damages can be prevented and the progression of the patient's chronic kidney disease can be reduced.

Glycemic Control

Despite the root cause of chronic kidney disease, tight glycemic control needs to be achieved for all diabetic individuals. The American Diabetic Association suggests a target glycosylated hemoglobin level of >7.0 for all diabetics, no matter whether kidney condition exists [17]. Therapy of diabetes in patients with kidney illness can be complicated. Table 5 shows diabetic medicines that need dosage modifications by creatinine clearance. Metformin, which is the keystone oral drug for diabetic glycemic control, is contraindicated with creatinine <1.5 in males and 1.4 in women due to the worry about lactic acidosis.

Cigarette Abuse

Smoking is related to a much more fast decline in kidney functionality despite the underlying reason for the chronic kidney condition [11]. Smoking cigarettes cessation need to be talked about and encouraged in all cigarette smokers with chronic kidney illness, specifically given that heart disease is the primary cause of mortality among this patient populace. Medications utilized to facilitate cigarette smoking cessation, such as Zyban (GlaxoSmithKline, Inc., Research Triangle Park, NC) and Chantix (Pfizer, New York, NY), require dose modifications in patients with kidney disease; however, these can still work adjuncts in support with successful smoking cessation.

Table 5: Dosage of Diabetic Medications in Chronic Kidney Disease[19].

Diabetic Medication	Renal Dosage
Biguanines	
Glucophage (metformin)	Renal impairment: avoid use
Sulfonureas	
Glucotrol (glipizide)	CrCl* <50: decrease dose by 50%
Diabeta (glyburide)	CrCl* <50: avoid use
Amaryl (glimepiride)	Renal impairment: start 1 mg daily, increase slowly, monitor glucose
Glitazones	
Actos (pioglitazone)	No adjustment
Avandia (rosiglitazone)	No adjustment
Alpha-glucosidase inhibitors	
Precose (acarbose)	Creatinine >2: avoid use
Glyset (miglitol)	Creatinine >2: avoid use
Meglitinides	
Starlix (nateglinide)	No adjustment
Prandin (repaglinide)	CrCl 20–40: start 0.5 mg before every meal, use titrate with caution CrCl <20: not defined
Incretin mimetics	
Byetta (exenatide)	CrCl 30–80: no adjustment CrCl <30 & HD: not recommended
Januvia (sitagliptin)	CrCl 30–49: 50 mg daily CrCl <30: 25 mg daily HD/CAPD: no supplement

* Calculated by Cockcroft-Gault equation.

Abbreviation: CrCl, creatinine clearance (mL/min); HD, hemodialysis; CAPD, continuous ambulatory peritoneal dialysis.

CONCLUSION:

Family physicians play a key function in ensuring that individuals with chronic kidney illness obtain proper counseling and health maintenance treatments; this is a pivotal part to effective management of chronic kidney disease. Immunizations that are suggested for all chronic kidney disease patients are influenza and pneumovax vaccinations. Once a patient develops stage 4 chronic kidney illness, they ought to likewise receive the hepatitis B series because hemodialysis patients are at a raised risk of exposure to hepatitis B, in spite of cautions. Diabetes mellitus and hypertension, which are frequently managed in the workplace setting, are the largest contributors to chronic kidney condition; for that reason, these danger aspects ought to be tightly controlled and these patients must be screened closely for indications of kidney damages. Further health maintenance measures should be executed according to the patient's other disease-specific suggestions and age.

Patients who smoke should be strongly encouraged to

try to quit cigarette smoking because smoking is associated with increased heart disease and has been shown to speed up the development of chronic kidney condition. Additionally, patients need to be stimulated to follow a healthy lifestyle with exercise as an element to combat their raised risk of cardiovascular disease.

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